

Towards 90 m resolution digital terrain model combining ICESat-2 and GEDI data: Balancing accuracy and sampling intensity

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ABSTRACT

This study employs Ice, Cloud and Elevation Satellite-2 (ICESat-2) and the Global Ecosystems Dynamics Investigation (GEDI) observations to generate gridded digital terrain models (DTMs). Specifically, we (1) compared how acquisition characteristics affect the accuracy of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations, (2) assessed the sampling intensity with respect to observation accuracy (0.25–50 m) and grid resolution (90, 300, and 1000 m), and (3) interpolated DTMs at 90 m resolution and compared their accuracy with a global digital elevation model (DEM) Copernicus GLO-90. ICESat-2 data consistently outperformed GEDI footprints in terms of terrain elevation accuracy across a range of conditions (terrain slope, landcover, beam strength, and day/night). Sampling intensity is strongly shaped by the trade-offs between observation accuracy and grid resolution, limiting the coverage at finer scales and stricter thresholds. However, combining ICESat-2 and GEDI boosted sampling intensity, with over 60 % of cells containing at least one observation, which enabled a 90 m DTMs interpolation. The spaceborne lidar DTMs at 90 m resolution achieved RMSEs between 9.9 and 14.7 m, comparable to Copernicus DEM (9.9–15.6 m). However, the local accuracy of the interpolated DTMs depended on both the number of input observations and their accuracy. Where at least 4–6 observations per a 90 m cell with vertical accuracy better than 5 m were available, spaceborne lidar DTMs outperformed the Copernicus DEM, with RMSEs of 3.7 m vs. 11.2 m in forests and 2.6 m vs. 3.1 m in non-forested areas. This demonstrates that spaceborne lidar-derived DTMs could replace global DEMs.

1. Introduction

Since the beginning of this century, significant prolific efforts have been devoted to producing global or near-global Digital Elevation Models (DEMs) using satellite data, either based on synthetic aperture radar (SAR) interferometry or optical imagery (Farr et al., 2007; Tachikawa et al., 2011; Wessel et al., 2018). The SRTM DEM (Farr et al., 2007) is probably the most widely used near-global DEM, followed by its successful successor, the TanDEM-X DEM (Krieger et al., 2013; Wessel et al., 2018). Other currently available global DEMs include ASTER GDEM (Tachikawa et al., 2011) and ALOS AW3D DEM (Tadono et al., 2015). These models enabled large-scales studies, supporting, among others, applications in hydrological modeling (Zhang et al., 2019; Xu

et al., 2022), species distribution modeling (Moudrý and Šimová, 2013), soil erosion modeling (Wang et al., 2023), and flood vulnerability assessment (Schumann and Bates, 2018).

However, despite their widespread use, the utility of these global DEMs remains constrained by the limited ability of SAR interferometry or optical imagery to capture true ground elevation, especially in vegetated areas (Hawker et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023). Most of the incoming signals are reflected by scatterers in the upper part of the canopy (Hofton et al., 2006). Consequently, the elevation values captured by the sensor are located somewhere between the ground and the top of the vegetation canopy, and all of the mentioned global DEMs are closer to Digital Surface Models (DSMs; i.e., the uppermost layer of the surface and includes all features present on the ground) than Digital

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Terrain Models (DTMs; i.e., records of the bare terrain without any objects on it) (Magruder et al., 2016; Schumann and Bates, 2018; Mouratidis and Ampatzidis, 2019; Gdulová et al., 2020). This fact can substantially influence downstream applications. For example, it can lead to errors in stream network delineation (Marešová et al., 2024) and flood modeling (Archer et al., 2018; Hawker et al., 2018; Garrote, 2022; Carlson et al., 2024). Therefore, the need for new remote sensing approaches for generating global DEMs that represent bare earth (i.e., DTMs) has been recently highlighted (Schumann and Bates, 2018; Simard et al., 2024).

Laser altimetry has emerged as an increasingly available alternative source of accurate global terrain information. Compared to interferometry or optical imagery, laser altimeters provide superior capability of capturing the terrain as they can penetrate the canopy gaps and directly measure ground elevation (Neuenschwander et al., 2020; Liu et al., 2022; Rodda et al., 2023). In 2018, NASA launched two groundbreaking spaceborne laser altimetry missions, namely Ice, Cloud, and Land Elevation Satellite-2 (ICESat-2) and Global Ecosystem Dynamics Investigation (GEDI), both of which provide highly accurate terrain elevation data (Neumann et al., 2019; Dubayah et al., 2020; Moudrý et al., 2022, 2024). However, the sampling intensity of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations remains relatively sparse (Potapov et al., 2021),

limiting their utility for producing high-resolution DTMs (Narin and Gullu, 2023; Cățeanu and Miculescu, 2024). Multiple studies have evaluated the accuracy of ICESat-2 (ATL08) and GEDI (L2A) products, which serve as the basis for the generation of DTMs, finding that their accuracy varies depending on environmental (e.g., land cover, cloud cover, slope) and measurement (e.g., beam strength) conditions (Neuenschwander et al., 2020; Quirós et al., 2021; Urbazaev et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2023; Moudrý et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024). Therefore, both ICESat-2 and GEDI observations require extensive filtering (i.e., removal of inaccurate observations), which further reduces the already limited number of observations useable for DTMs generation. This brings a trade-off between the accuracy of observations and sampling intensity (we can distinguish between density, i.e., the number of observations per cell, and coverage, i.e., the number of grid cells containing the sufficient number of observations of required accuracy). As a result, gridded global terrain height products from both missions are available only at a 1 km resolution (Dubayah et al., 2021; Guenther et al., 2023).

One potential solution to the issue of the limited number of high-quality observations is to combine ICESat-2 and GEDI observations to increase sampling intensity, which may allow interpolation of higher-resolution DTMs (Tian and Shan, 2023; Narin and Gullu, 2023; Pronk et al., 2024; Zhao et al., 2025). So far, however, no study has thoroughly

Fig. 1. Processing workflow. Observations from ICESat-2 (ATL08 segments) and GEDI (L2A footprints) were filtered using two independent approaches: the first uses internal flags, while the second relied on auxiliary ALS-derived DTMs. These two approaches were in the subsequent steps used to assess the role of observations accuracy on quality of interpolated DTMs. Filtered observations entered the first step in which the role of acquisition and environmental characteristics for ICESat-2 and GEDI accuracy was evaluated (Section 2.6). In the subsequent step, the trade-off between sampling intensity, accuracy, and resolution was assessed (Section 2.7), and combined ICESat-2 and GEDI observations were used to interpolate spaceborne lidar DTMs (Section 2.8). The most accurate approach (i.e., combination of observations accuracy and sampling intensity) for generating spaceborne lidar DTMs was selected and compared with Copernicus DEM (Section 2.9).

explored how vertical accuracy and sampling intensity of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations influence the quality of resulting DTMs. Here, therefore, we evaluate the trade-off between the selected accuracy threshold and resulting sampling intensity of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations and examine how this trade-off affects DTMs production at three spatial resolutions (90, 300, and 1000 m) across study areas on three continents. Specifically, we (1) investigate how environmental conditions (i.e., slope, landcover, solar angle) and sensor parameters (i.e., beam strength) affect the accuracy of ATL08 and L2A observations; (2) assess the sampling intensity of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations in relation to their accuracy and the target DEM resolution; (3) interpolate DTMs based on combined ICESat-2 and GEDI observations at a 90 m resolution with different observation accuracy thresholds (hereafter referred to as spaceborne lidar DTMs); and (4) compare the accuracy of the resulting interpolated DTMs with that of the Copernicus DEM to assess their potential for improving bare-earth terrain representation of global models (see Fig. 1 for the overall workflow of the study). We expect the spaceborne lidar DTMs to yield higher accuracy in forested areas and to perform similarly well to the Copernicus DEM in non-forested areas. Our results will indicate whether ICESat-2 and GEDI observations can be used in the near future to generate DTMs in countries where more accurate data (e.g., from airborne laser scanning) are not available and which, therefore, still rely on global DEMs, such as Copernicus DEM.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Study areas

We selected three study areas located in Switzerland, New Zealand, California (USA). The areas were selected based on the availability of reference lidar data between 2019 and 2023 corresponding to the temporal coverage of GEDI and ICESat-2 (Table 1; Fig. 2) as well as challenging terrain topography and vegetation cover. The Entlebuch Biosphere Reserve is located in the central Switzerland. It includes the cultural landscape of Entlebuch, which has been designated as a UNESCO Biosphere Reserve (40,000 ha) since 2001. The region consists primarily of pre-alpine and alpine mountain ranges, forests, agriculturally used meadows, and small settlements. Elevations range from 500 m to 2350 m. Beech (*Fagus sylvatica*) is typically the naturally dominant species at lower elevations, while at higher elevations, spruce (*Picea abies*) and larch (*Larix decidua*) prevail (<https://www.unesco.org/en>).

The Marlborough study area is located in the northern part of New Zealand's South Island. It covers much of the Marlborough region, particularly the Mount Richmond Forest Park and the Wairau River valley, and covers more than 330,000 ha. Mount Richmond Forest Park was established in 1977. It is a mountainous landscape, with elevations ranging from 0 to 1760 m, covered with a dense forest including native beech and plantation forests (*Nothofagus* spp.), dense stands of native mānuka (*Leptospermum scoparium*) and kānuka (*Leptospermum ericoides*), as well as pastures. South of the Wairau River, grasslands are the predominant vegetation cover.

The Trinity Alps Wilderness is situated in Northern California, USA,

Table 1
Airborne laser scanning data characteristics.

Study area	Area (ha)	Year	Horizontal datum/ Projection	Vertical datum	Point density
Entlebuch	40,000	2019	CH1903+	LV95	5 p/m ²
Marlborough	330,000	2020–2021	NZGD 2000 Transverse Mercator	NZVD2016	9 p/m ²
Trinity	250,000	2019–2020	NAD83 (2011) UTM zone 10N	NAVD 88	8 p/m ²

within the Klamath Mountains subrange. The study area encompasses over 250,000 ha, characterized by a rugged mountainous landscape with steep river canyons. The elevations range from 600 m to 2750 m. The area is covered with dense forests, including mixed conifer forests (e.g., *Pinus ponderosa*, *Abies concolor*, *Pseudotsuga menziesii*), red fir forests (e.g., *Abies magnifica*, *Pinus monticola*), and subalpine forests (e.g., *Pinus balfouriana*, *Pinus albicaulis*) (Ferlatte, 1974; Garwood and Welsh, 2007).

2.2. Reference airborne laser scanning data

The airborne lidar data for the Entlebuch Biosphere Reserve were collected in 2019 (Table 1) as part of an acquisition campaign to obtain Switzerland-wide lidar data. The minimum point density of this dataset referenced to CH1903+/LV95 (EPSG:2056) is 5 points per m². The Federal Office of Topography in Switzerland reports the planimetric and altimetric accuracies of the dataset to be 20 cm and 10 cm (1 σ), respectively. The airborne lidar data for the Mount Richmond Forest were collected between 2020 and 2021 (Table 1) as part of an acquisition campaign aiming to obtain New Zealand's national elevation model. The average point density is 9 points per m² and the dataset is referenced to NZGD2000/New Zealand Transverse Mercator 2000 (EPSG:2193). According to the National Elevation Programme of New Zealand, the minimum planimetric and altimetric accuracies are 50 cm and 10 cm, respectively, for both vegetated and non-vegetated areas. The airborne lidar data for the Trinity Alps were collected between 2019 and 2020 (Table 1), as part of the 3D Elevation Program (3DEP), with an average point density of 8 points per m² referenced to NAD83(2011)/UTM zone 10N (EPSG: 6339). The minimum absolute vertical accuracy of this dataset (95 % confidence level) is 30 cm in vegetated areas and 20 cm in non-vegetated terrain (Stoker and Miller, 2022). All point clouds were already classified by their respective vendors. Digital terrain models for all three areas were generated using returns classified as ground using the las2dem tool in LAStools (version 220613) at a 2 m resolution. This tool triangulates ground returns into a Triangulated Irregular Network (TIN), which is then converted into a raster DEM. In addition, we used the generated DTMs to calculate slope at a 2 m resolution for each study area using Horn's algorithm implemented in ArcGIS Pro.

2.3. Reference global DEM

The TanDEM-X mission yielded a truly global (pole to pole) DEM, referred to as the TanDEM-X DEM (Krieger et al., 2013; Zink et al., 2014). The TanDEM-X DEM represents an unedited version of the data. It contains voids resulting, e.g., from unprocessable observations. This model was further edited, resulting in the release of the Copernicus DEM (publicly available since December 2019). The Copernicus DEM is mostly based on TanDEM-X DEM; to some extent, however, additional global DEMs (such as SRTM and ASTER GDEM) were used to fill voids or reduce the error in problematic areas (Marešová et al., 2021). Here, we used the Copernicus DEM data (GLO-90), available from <https://dataspace.copernicus.eu/> (requires registration). The Copernicus DEM is referenced to the WGS84 horizontal and EGM2008 vertical reference systems, and it was transformed into the local horizontal coordinate systems using the bilinear resampling method.

2.4. ICESat-2 ATL08 and GEDI L2A

The ICESat-2 satellite was launched by NASA in September 2018 (Markus et al., 2017). Besides its primary goal of mapping the cryosphere (Farrell et al., 2020), it provides a wide range of scientific data with global spatial coverage (Magruder et al., 2021, 2024). The satellite carries the Advanced Topographic Laser Altimetry System (ATLAS) on board, which uses a unique single-photon counting approach and enables measurement of the Earth's surface with less pulse energy

Fig. 2. Locations of the three study areas (Switzerland, New Zealand, and California), and the density of ICESat-2 (blue) and GEDI (green) observations.

(compared to full-waveform lidar). This, in turn, leads to a much higher repetition frequency (10 kHz), producing overlapping footprints of 11–12 m in diameter at intervals of approximately 0.7 m along the track (Magruder et al., 2021). ATLAS emits six beams at a wavelength of 532 nm, divided into three beam pairs consisting of a strong and weak beam with an energy ratio of approximately 4:1.

The GEDI instrument was successfully installed on the International Space Station (ISS) in December 2018 and collected data for more than four years, until March 2023. After temporary decommissioning, GEDI resumed data acquisition in April 2024. Data coverage is limited to latitudes between 51.6°N and 51.6°S due to the ISS orbit. An advanced 1064 nm full-waveform laser was specifically designed for monitoring terrain and vegetation structure. It employs three lasers — two strong beams and one additional beam split into two coverage beams. Each laser captures 242 observations per second, generating circular footprints on the Earth's surface with a diameter of 25 m. GEDI generates eight footprints spaced 600 m apart, with a total swath width of 4.2 km (Dubayah et al., 2020).

ICESat-2 data are available in several data products depending on the data processing level. Here, we used the ATL08 data product. For our analysis, we employed the "h_te_best" parameter representing the terrain elevation at the mid-point of each 20 m segment. For GEDI, we used the L2A Elevation and Height Metrics data product version 2 (Dubayah et al., 2020), which provides terrain elevation estimates for each laser footprint. The returned waveform is typically multimodal, with the lowest mode "elev_lowestmode" representing the terrain elevation. The ATL08 (version 6) dataset used in this study contains data from 2018 to mid-2024, while the GEDI L2A product (version 2) includes data collected between April 2019 and April 2023. Both were accessed through NASA's Earthdata portal in July 2024.

Both ATL08 and L2A are referenced to WGS84 using ellipsoidal heights, whereas the ALS reference data use orthometric or normal heights. To match the vertical datum, we used CHGeo2004 geoid for the study area in Switzerland, NZ Quasigeoid 2016 for the New Zealand area, and the GEOID18 geoid for the Californian study area, respectively. In order to match the horizontal datum with ALS data, we also projected horizontal coordinates of ATL08 segments and L2A footprints data into the local coordinate system of each study area (Table 1).

2.5. Observations filtering

2.5.1. Filtering using internal flags

Both ATL08 and GEDI L2A datasets include flags that describe surface characteristics (e.g., reflectance, elevation) and atmospheric conditions during acquisition, helping users to assess data reliability and perform observations filtering. Therefore, the first filtering scenario (hereafter S_F) used a series of filters using these flags in both ICESat-2 ATL08 and GEDI L2A datasets based on the recommendations from existing studies (Adam et al., 2020; Moudrý et al., 2022, 2024; Urbazaev et al., 2022) to exclude low-quality observations.

First, we removed outliers, i.e., ICESat-2 and GEDI observations with absolute elevation differences greater than 100 m from global DEM. The threshold was selected based on recommendations published in recent studies: a too low threshold (e.g., 50 m) may result in the exclusion of otherwise valid observations. In forested areas, such as those in our study, it has been recommended to use higher thresholds (e.g. 100 m) (Moudrý et al., 2022, 2024; Urbazaev et al., 2022). In addition, we excluded all ICESat-2 ATL08 and GEDI L2A observations from areas with slopes exceeding 50° because they are generally known to be inaccurate (Pronk et al., 2024). We did not apply any geolocation correction because the finest resolution we were aiming for was 90 m and the typical geolocation error is lower than the mission specification of 6.5 m for ICESat-2 (Neuenschwander and Magruder, 2019; Bae et al., 2021) and 10 m for GEDI footprints (Tang et al., 2023a), respectively. For GEDI L2A, additional filters were applied: we retained only observations with Quality Flag = 1 and Degrade Flag = 0, and excluded noise footprints with fewer than one return mode (Moudrý et al., 2024). This resulted in 99,136; 640,256; and 644,761 observations retained for DTMs generation in Entlebuch, Marlborough, and Trinity, respectively (Fig. 2). This scenario reflects the common situation where users rely on internal flags to filter spaceborne observations.

2.5.2. Filtering using ALS-derived DTM

The other approach was to filter ICESat-2 and GEDI observations based on a comparison with highly accurate ALS-derived DTMs, which allowed us to select observations with known absolute accuracies. This approach was applied in nine scenarios with observations selected based on the maximum elevation errors, defined as an elevation difference between the terrain measured by space-borne lidar ("h_te_best" for ICESat-2 and "elev_lowestmode" for GEDI, respectively) and a

reference ALS-derived DTMs. The nine maximum elevation error thresholds used in filtering scenarios were 0.25 m, 0.5 m, 1.0 m, 5.0 m, 10 m, 15 m, 20 m, 30 m and 50 m (hereafter referred to as S_025, S_05, S_1, S_5, S_10, S_15, S_20, S_30, S_50). These maximum elevation error thresholds for filtering scenarios were selected to span a range of filtering stringencies, from very high accuracy (0.25–1 m), through moderate accuracy (5–15 m), which, given the typical accuracies reported by validation studies (RMSEs between 1 and 10 m; Neuenschwander et al., 2020; Quirós et al., 2021; Urbazaev et al., 2022; Feng et al., 2023; Moudrý et al., 2024), we consider the most realistic scenarios in our study, to low accuracy (20–50 m). This was to evaluate how model performance degrades as the allowable elevation error increases. Note that this approach cannot be used in areas where ALS DTM is not available. However, for the purposes of this study, it allows us to assess how changing the error tolerance affects the density of retained observations and, consequently, the quality of the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs.

2.6. Role of acquisition and environmental characteristics for ICESat-2 and GEDI accuracy

Similar to several prior studies, we assessed the influence of acquisition and environmental characteristics on the accuracies of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations. We used observations filtered using flags and auxiliary data (Section 2.5.1) to evaluate the influence of signal strength (i.e., ICESat-2 strong or weak beams and GEDI power or coverage beams) and acquisition time (day/night, represented by solar elevation – positive values for daytime, negative for nighttime) on observations accuracy. Additionally, terrain slope is a well-established source of error in spaceborne lidar measurements (e.g., Chen, 2010; Quirós et al., 2021). To quantify the effect of slope, we derived slope rasters from ALS DTMs at 1 m resolution and computed the average slope within each ICESat-2 20 m segment and each GEDI 25 m footprint. We used Horn’s algorithm with a 3×3 cell neighborhood implemented in the Slope tool of ArcGIS Pro (version 3.4.0). We distinguished three slope categories: GENTLE/MODERATE (0° – 15°), STEEP (15° – 30°), VERY STEEP (30° – 50°). In addition, we assessed the role of land cover, distinguishing two categories – Forest and Non-Forest (including Shrubland, Grassland, Cropland, and Bare/Sparse Vegetation), which were evaluated separately. Information about land cover was extracted from the ESA world cover raster in 10 m resolution (<https://esa-worldcover.org/en>) for the year 2020 (Zanaga et al., 2021).

2.7. Balancing sampling intensity, accuracy, and resolution for DTM interpolation

To assess the sampling intensity (i.e., coverage and density) of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations with respect to their vertical error and the target DEM resolution, and to assess the optimal balance between resolution and accuracy for generating a DTM, we considered three spatial resolutions (90, 300, 1000 m) and ten elevation error scenarios (i.e., S_025, S_05, S_1, S_5, S_15, S_20, S_30, S_50, S_F, see above). These scenarios reflect the various qualities of input data for the creation of DTMs. We selected the resolutions to represent key reference scales: 90 m, which served as our primary target resolution and corresponds to typical global DEMs; 1000 m, matching the native resolution of DTMs derived from the ICESat-2 and GEDI missions; and an intermediate resolution of 300 m. We computed sampling intensity (observation densities and coverage) for each combination of maximum elevation error threshold scenario and resolution.

2.8. Spaceborne lidar DTM interpolation

Interpolation was performed at a 90 m resolution using the combined ICESat-2 and GEDI dataset. This was because it was the best resolution at which valid measurements were available in at least 50 % of the grid

cells at the accuracy of 5 m, i.e., the scenario S_5, (and, of course, at all inferior accuracies). Following Tian and Shan (2023), we chose Natural Neighbor interpolation to generate the 90 m resolution raster. This approach is a robust, parameter-free method that locally adapts to the distribution of input data, making it particularly suitable for irregular and variable-density observations. It is important to note that we did not perform simple aggregation (e.g., mean or median) of multiple ICESat-2 or GEDI points within a cell; instead, each point contributed to the interpolated surface according to the Natural Neighbor algorithm, which adaptively weights nearby observations. Given the known low density of the ICESat-2 and GEDI observations, we chose 90 m as the finest target resolution, and did not employ the finer resolution of 30 m now common for global DEMs. The reason was that, as recently shown by Narin and Gullu (2023), the density of observations at a 30 m resolution is too low and DTMs generated from spaceborne lidar at such a fine resolution perform worse than existing global DEMs.

2.9. Accuracy assessment and comparison to global DEM

To evaluate the vertical accuracy of spaceborne lidar data and their suitability for generating DTMs, we analyzed three different elevation datasets: (i) elevation observations from spaceborne lidar, (ii) spaceborne lidar DTMs interpolated from ICESat-2 and GEDI observations, and (iii) an existing global DEM, namely the Copernicus DEM. We also performed a direct visual comparison between the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs and the existing global Copernicus DEM.

The vertical error was calculated as the difference between the evaluated elevation value (from ICESat-2, GEDI, the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs, or the global DEM, respectively) and the reference surface derived from the corresponding ALS DTM. For ICESat-2 (ATL08), terrain elevation at the midpoint of each 20 m segment was used. For GEDI (L2A), the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs, and Copernicus DEM, we aggregated the ALS reference DTM (using the mean value) to match the size of the respective model cell/footprint. To summarize the error distributions, we employed two standard accuracy metrics.

- Mean error (ME):

$$ME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (h_i - h_{ref})$$

- Root Mean Square Error (RMSE):

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (h_i - h_{ref})^2}$$

where h_i represents the i th elevation value from the evaluated product (ATL08, L2A, spaceborne lidar DTMs, Copernicus DEM), h_{ref} is the corresponding elevation from the ALS reference DTM, and n is the number of samples.

3. Results

3.1. Accuracy of ATL08 segments and L2A footprints after filtering according to flags

We observed strong agreement between ICESat-2 terrain heights filtered as described in Section 2.5.1. and the reference DTMs. Across all three study areas, the overall ME of ICESat-2 terrain height was better than -1.4 m, while the RMSE remained below 3.3 m (Table 2). The agreement was considerably lower for GEDI terrain height. Nevertheless, the overall ME of GEDI remained lower than -2.5 m, and the RMSE stayed below 10.3 m across all three study areas (Table 2).

Table 2
Accuracy measures of ICESat-2 (ATL08) and GEDI (L2A) observations in the three study areas.

		ME [m]	RMSE [m]	number of observations
Entlebuch	ICESat-2	-1.1	2.4	54,086
	GEDI	-1.0	8.9	45,050
Marlborough	ICESat-2	0.2	3.3	277,308
	GEDI	-0.5	10.3	362,948
Trinity	ICESat-2	-1.4	3.0	318,625
	GEDI	-2.5	8.3	326,136

A detailed accuracy assessment considering environmental conditions revealed that ICESat-2 terrain height observations were more accurate during nighttime acquisitions compared to daytime. For GEDI, however, this day–night effect was not clearly evident and varied across locations and beam types (Table 3). In ICESat-2, the accuracy of nighttime observations was comparable between strong and weak beams, whereas during daytime, the strong beam performed considerably better. When comparing the accuracy of ICESat-2 in non-forested areas and forests, it was typically similar or slightly lower in forests. In the case of GEDI, the differences were less pronounced; however, when focusing on areas with relatively low slopes, higher accuracy was also observed in non-forested areas. Finally, the accuracy of both datasets decreased with an increasing slope; with a greater detrimental effect on GEDI. On steep slopes, the RMSE of ICESat-2 was only slightly worse than that of GEDI on flat terrain (Table 3).

3.2. Sampling intensity

The patterns of sampling intensity (i.e., density and coverage) were consistent across the study areas. The sampling density of ICESat-2 or GEDI observations considerably decreased with finer resolution and a higher accuracy threshold. For example, a resolution of 300 m combined with a vertical accuracy better than 5 m resulted in a median density of

two observations per cell for ICESat-2 and 8 observations per cell for GEDI, respectively (Fig. 3).

The spatial coverage of both ICESat-2 and GEDI considerably increased when the requirements on observations density and accuracy were relaxed. GEDI generally provided better coverage than ICESat-2, especially when higher point densities and finer resolution were required. However, for very strict accuracy scenarios (S_025, S_05) ICESat-2 provided better coverage in some cases (Fig. 4). Combining ICESat-2 and GEDI data substantially improved both density (Fig. 3) and coverage (Fig. 4), especially at finer resolutions or under strict accuracy thresholds. However, when increasing the stringency of accuracy thresholds and the requirements on density, fewer observations met the criteria, resulting in poor spatial coverage even when the datasets were combined. When comparing the results from both filtering approaches (i.e., using ALS-derived DTM and using flags (S_F)), the coverage of the latter approach was comparable with that obtained using accuracy threshold of 5 m in the former approach (S_5 scenario).

Generally, resolution was the most important factor affecting both density (Fig. 3) and coverage (Fig. 4). At a resolution of 1 km, more than 10 points were available in most of the cells for combined and GEDI datasets even with an accuracy threshold of 1 m (scenario S_1). The combined dataset achieved almost complete coverage with a density of more than 5 points per cell at a resolution of 300 m, provided that the accuracy requirements were low (i.e., observation error greater than 5 m; Fig. 4). However, at a resolution of 90 m, both ICESat-2 and GEDI showed low observations densities (Fig. 3) and limited coverage, especially for higher point densities. However, combining them considerably boosted coverage, especially when requirements on point densities were low (Fig. 4).

3.3. Role of sampling intensity for accuracy of interpolated 90m resolution DTMs

Based on the above analysis of sampling intensity, we concluded that interpolation of a 90 m resolution DTM using the combined ICESat-2 and

Table 3
Root mean squared errors (RMSEs) of ICESat-2 (ALT08) and GEDI (L2A) terrain height in meters with respect to steepness of slope, solar angle, landcover, time of acquisition, and beam strength (green – lowest error; purple – highest error).

		Entlebuch				Marlborough				Trinity				
		Non-Forest		Forest		Non-Forest		Forest		Non-Forest		Forest		
Slope category	Day / Night	Strong/ Power	Weak/ Cover.											
ICESat-2	GENTLE / MODERATE	day	1.2	2.1	1.5	2.1	0.8	0.9	2.5	2.0	1.7	2.3	1.5	2.1
		night	0.9	0.8	1.2	1.1	0.6	0.8	2.2	2.0	1.5	1.4	1.2	1.2
	STEEP	day	2.3	3.5	2.7	3.4	2.7	3.4	5.3	5.3	2.9	4.1	2.8	3.6
		night	2.0	1.8	2.1	2.1	1.9	1.8	4.0	3.5	2.2	2.2	2.2	2.3
VERY STEEP	day	4.0	5.7	4.4	5.1	4.0	5.4	6.7	7.0	4.3	5.5	4.2	5.3	
	night	3.6	3.2	3.9	3.6	3.4	2.6	5.1	5.0	3.9	3.7	3.5	3.6	
GEDI	GENTLE / MODERATE	day	4.8	2.0	5.7	3.6	1.8	2.0	4.3	4.9	3.0	2.2	3.6	3.0
		night	3.7	9.4	2.9	7.4	9.0	7.2	9.0	10.1	5.5	2.6	6.8	4.6
	STEEP	day	6.0	4.7	8.0	6.8	6.8	7.3	7.6	9.0	4.3	5.3	5.9	5.9
		night	4.8	13.9	5.2	10.5	13.9	14.7	10.4	11.6	11.2	9.0	8.4	7.5
VERY STEEP	day	8.7	7.7	13.1	11.6	12.1	12.0	9.9	10.7	8.6	8.4	8.7	8.3	
	night	12.8	14.1	9.0	13.6	16.2	15.6	11.8	12.3	14.6	13.0	11.1	10.4	

Fig. 3. Sampling density of ICESat-2 (ATL08), GEDI (L2A), and their combination with respect to resolution and accuracy scenarios.

GEDI dataset is feasible as at that resolution, at least one observation was present in 60 % of cells in the S_5 scenario as well as in all scenarios with lower accuracy thresholds. However, under high-accuracy scenarios (S_025, S_05, S_01), the coverage dropped well below 50 % (Fig. 4). In all regions, the best RMSE values were observed in filtering scenarios using vertical thresholds of 15 m (S_15) or 20 m (S_20). Stricter vertical thresholds led to a considerable reduction in sampling intensity (see Section 3.2; Fig. 4) and, therefore, a rapid increase in the number of observation-free cells. This, in turn, caused a decline in DTM accuracy. Less strict thresholds, on the other hand, included observations of low accuracy, reducing DTMs accuracy across all study areas (Fig. 5).

The mean error was less affected by filtering scenarios than RMSE, and the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs underestimated the terrain in both forest and non-forest areas (Fig. 5). In terms of RMSE, the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs performed better in non-forested than in forested areas, except for the Trinity study area (Fig. 5). DTMs generated using scenarios with observations filtered using ALS-derived DTMs performed better than DTMs generated using observations filtered using internal flags (i.e., of unknown accuracy; S_F), underscoring the importance of accurate filtering for the quality of the resulting DTM.

A closer look revealed that the accuracy of spaceborne lidar DTMs varied considerably between individual cells and that their accuracy depended on the density and accuracy of the input observations. Comparing the accuracy of spaceborne lidar DTMs based on the observation density showed that the accuracy improved considerably with each additional observation within a cell. This improvement was highest between observation-free cells and cells with 1–3 observations (Fig. 6). Lower, but still considerable, improvement was observed with density increase to 4 to 6 observations (Fig. 6). With further density increase, the accuracy improvement is much slower. When only cells with observation densities of 10 or more per 90 m cell were used and only observations with accuracy better than 5 m were included (i.e., filtering scenario S_5), the accuracy of spaceborne lidar DTMs improved to RMSEs below 3 m across all study areas and in both forested and non-forested areas (Fig. 6).

3.4. Accuracy of interpolated DTMs versus accuracy of Copernicus DEM

A comparison of the Copernicus DEM and spaceborne lidar DTMs using the accuracy scenario S_15, which performed best among the tested scenarios (see above), showed that in forests, spaceborne lidar

DTMs at this scenario outperformed the Copernicus DEM. The only exception was found in forested areas in Marlborough, where it performed slightly worse (Fig. 5). In contrast, the Copernicus DEM surpassed the accuracy (in terms of RMSE) of the spaceborne lidar DTMs in non-forested areas across all study sites. While the difference was minimal in Entlebuch, Copernicus DEM performed considerably better in Marlborough, and especially in Trinity. In addition, the comparison with ALS-derived DTMs showed a positive vertical offset of Copernicus DEM in all land cover classes, while the spaceborne lidar DTMs tended to underestimate the terrain (Fig. 5; Fig. 7). In non-forested areas, the height error density plots for all models show a unimodal distribution with the center of the distribution around zero. In forests, the center of height error distribution of the Copernicus DEM shifted into positive values, while spaceborne lidar DTMs show a unimodal distribution with the center of the distribution around zero (Fig. 8).

A closer look revealed that whether the spaceborne lidar DTMs outperformed the Copernicus DEM or not largely depended on observation density (Fig. 6). In forested areas, the accuracy of spaceborne lidar models was poorer than that of the Copernicus DEM only in the observation-free cells; as soon as one to three observations were present in the cell, spaceborne lidar DTMs already outperformed the Copernicus DEM, regardless of the (accuracy) filtering scenarios. In contrast, in non-forested areas, at least four to six observations per cell, along with the use of moderate-accuracy filtering scenarios, were required for the spaceborne lidar DTMs to outperform the Copernicus DEM (Fig. 6). This highlights the importance of filtering ICESat-2 (ATL08) and GEDI (L2A) observations for generating accurate DTMs.

4. Discussion

As the demand for accurate global DEMs continues to grow, new data sources for constructing models with the best possible reliability are being investigated. Recent spaceborne lidar missions have shown particular potential for such a purpose. Here, we used data from ICESat-2 and GEDI to generate DTMs and assess trade-offs between observation accuracy, sampling intensity, and spatial resolution.

4.1. Accuracy of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations and factors influencing it

Our results show that ICESat-2 ATL08 (20 m segments) considerably outperforms GEDI L2A (25 m footprints) in terrain height estimation

Fig. 4. Relationships between the accuracy scenarios (values indicate absolute differences from reference data in meters), density (number of observations per cell), and spatial coverage (percent of cells with respective densities) of ATL08 and L2A elevation observations, evaluated at three different resolutions (90, 300, and 1000 m). The figure illustrates trade-offs among these variables, highlighting how the choice of resolution and observations accuracy affect sampling intensity (i.e., coverage and density). Note the improvement in sampling intensity when combining ICESat-2 (ATL08) and GEDI (L2A), and be aware of the different scales on the vertical axes. As patterns were consistent across study areas, results were aggregated.

across all study areas (Table 3). This is consistent with previous studies that have also found ICESat-2 to outperform GEDI for terrain height estimation (e.g., Liu et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2023; Pronk et al., 2024; Căţeanu and Miclescu, 2024; Fu et al., 2025). Interestingly, the opposite trend is typically observed for canopy height estimation, where GEDI typically performs better (Liu et al., 2021; Zhu et al., 2022; Fu et al., 2025). While some have argued that comparisons between the two sensors may be inappropriate due to differences in footprint size (Urbazaev et al., 2022), with ICESat-2 ATL08 segments covering approximately 20×11 m (220 m^2) and GEDI L2A footprints having 25 m in diameter (490 m^2), this difference in size should not considerably affect terrain height accuracy in flat terrain. Yet, ICESat-2 continues to outperform GEDI even there (Table 3). This may be attributed to several factors, including ICESat-2’s photon-counting approach, which is more successful at detecting the ground surface, or its superior geolocation accuracy. Additionally, differences in processing algorithms and

sensitivity to varying measurement conditions may further contribute to ICESat-2’s superior performance in terrain height estimation (see further below).

ICESat-2 and GEDI differed in sensitivity to evaluated measurement conditions (slope, day/night, beam power, land cover; Table 3). Our results revealed that ICESat-2 nighttime acquisitions outperformed daytime ones, with similar accuracies observed for the strong and weak beams at night. During the day, however, the strong beam performed considerably better than the weak one. This trend was consistent across all study areas and can be attributed to the photon-counting approach of ICESat-2, where the increased background noise from solar illumination during daytime acquisitions—combined with the lower density of signal photons in the weak beam—makes reliable identification of ground signal photons more difficult (Neuenschwander et al., 2022; Varvia et al., 2022). In the case of GEDI, no day–night difference was evident, varying across locations as well as land cover and beam types, while

Fig. 5. Root mean square errors (RMSEs) and mean errors (ME) of spaceborne lidar DTMs (constructed by natural neighbor interpolation from combined ICESat-2 and GEDI observations) across all three study areas, using different accuracy thresholds compared to ALS reference DTMs (DTM_S5-DTM_S50) in forested and non-forested areas. For comparison, the RMSEs and MEs of DTMs constructed based on internal ICESat-2 and GEDI flag filtering (DTM_SF) and Copernicus DEM (DEM_COP) are also included.

other studies reported GEDI to provide similar or lower errors in daytime observations than at nighttime (Zhu et al., 2023; Pronk et al., 2024). On the other hand, an unexpected pattern of daytime observations being more accurate than nighttime ones was observed by Wang et al. (2022). The reason for the better accuracy of daytime acquisitions at certain sites remains unclear, but it may reflect site-specific conditions (e.g., the effect of clouds; Fayad et al. (2021); Moudrý et al. (2022)) or differences in data quality filtering between study areas.

When comparing ICESat-2 accuracy between non-forested and forested areas, it was generally comparable but tended to be slightly lower in forests. For GEDI, the differences were even less apparent; however, more accurate observations were found in non-forested areas, particularly in regions with gentle or moderate slopes. Terrain slope consistently emerges as the most influential factor affecting the accuracy of terrain height estimates from both ICESat-2 and GEDI (Table 3), with steeper slopes leading to greater errors (Liu et al., 2021; Urbazaev et al., 2022; Zhu et al., 2023; Pronk et al., 2024; Fu et al., 2025).

Our results show that the effect of slope is especially pronounced for GEDI, with the accuracy of ICESat-2 in very steep terrain (slopes exceeding 30°) is comparable to that of GEDI in gentle/moderately steep

terrain (slopes below 15°; Table 3). This may be attributed to the smaller footprint size of ICESat-2 (~12 m) compared to GEDI (~25 m), as well as its lower horizontal geolocation error (Urbazaev et al., 2022; Pronk et al., 2024). Terrain height accuracy generally decreases with increasing footprint size (Chen, 2010). Combined with geolocation error – which is up to 10 m in the case of GEDI (Tang et al., 2023a) – these two factors can explain the observed differences in performance between the two datasets. Footprint geolocation corrections (e.g., Hancock et al., 2019; Tang et al., 2023a) may help to reduce these errors, but reported effectiveness varies across studies (Moudrý et al., 2024). The fundamental difference in how ICESat-2 and GEDI record and process (i.e., ground filter) the returned signal is another possible explanation. ICESat-2 uses single-photon counting to detect individual signal photons and generates a point cloud from which ground returns are identified. In contrast, GEDI records full waveforms and estimates ground elevation by fitting models to the waveform. As terrain slope increases, waveform extents are broadened, ground mode becomes obscured, and distinguishing between ground and vegetation signals becomes more difficult due to signal mixing (Chen, 2010; Ni et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2024). Single-photon lidar systems such as ICESat-2 are less affected by

Fig. 6. Effect of combined (ICESat-2 + GEDI) observation density within a cell and accuracy thresholds used to filter the observations (filtering scenarios) on the RMSEs of spaceborne lidar DTMs interpolated using natural neighbors. Observations were filtered (i) using an auxiliary ALS DTM to acquire only observations with respective accuracy thresholds (5–50 m; DTM_S5 – DTM_S50), and (ii) using internal ICESat-2 and GEDI quality flags (DTM_SF). Solid lines represent spaceborne lidar DTMs; the dashed lines show Copernicus DEM, evaluated in the cells with the corresponding observation density. Note that compared to forested areas, stricter filtering scenarios and higher observation densities are required in non-forested areas to generate more accurate spaceborne lidar DTMs than Copernicus DEM.

this issue, as ground elevation is estimated through interpolation of discrete ground returns. In summary, the consistently lower RMSE of ICESat-2 compared to GEDI (Table 3) likely reflects a combination of factors, with photon-counting enabling more reliable ground detection, smaller footprint size and higher geolocation accuracy reducing slope-induced errors, and algorithmic differences further amplifying the advantage. This highlights the advantage of single-photon lidar for terrain mapping, supporting its consideration as a preferred approach for future satellite missions targeting global terrain monitoring.

It is worth noting that temporal misalignment between the datasets used in this study may have slightly influenced our results. Although we attempted to minimize this effect by selecting reference ALS data from 2019 to 2021, which overlaps with the acquisition period of ICESat-2 and GEDI data (2018–2024), it does not coincide with the Copernicus DEM, which was generated primarily from TanDEM-X mission data collected between 2011 and 2015 (Hajsek et al., 2025). Due to the limited availability of data, it is common practice to assess the accuracy

of global DEMs using reference datasets acquired at different times, with differences of several years being common (e.g., Kolecka and Kozak, 2014; Hawker et al., 2019; Kramm and Hoffmeister, 2022). Our study follows this approach, and the timing of data acquisition—particularly with regard to the Copernicus DEM—should be considered when interpreting the results.

4.2. Role of sampling intensity, observation accuracy, and spatial resolution in DTMs generation

The results reveal clear trade-offs between sampling intensity (i.e., density and coverage), observation accuracy of the ICESat-2 and GEDI datasets, and the spatial resolution targeted for DTM generation. Naturally, resolution emerges as the dominant factor influencing spatial coverage: at coarser resolutions (e.g., 1 km), near-complete coverage can be achieved even with moderate accuracy thresholds of 5–15 m, whereas at finer resolutions (e.g., 90 m), coverage is much more

Fig. 7. Visualizations of terrain height differences (error) between the spaceborne lidar DTM and Copernicus DEM, respectively, against the reference ALS-derived DTM in all three study areas. For comparison, slope and land cover (forested vs non-forested area) are also visualized. Note that Copernicus DEM tended to overestimate terrain height, especially in forested areas, while spaceborne lidar DTM generally underestimated it.

Fig. 8. Density plots of height errors for the Copernicus DEM (DEM_COP) and interpolated lidar DTMs (DTM_S15, 15 m threshold). Two-sample Kolmogorov–Smirnov (KS) tests reveal large, significant differences in forested areas (KS_D = 0.489–0.632, $p < 0.001$) and smaller but noticeable differences in non-forest areas (KS_D = 0.249–0.303, $p < 0.001$), indicating that DEM differences are amplified in vegetated terrain.

sensitive to accuracy filtering (Fig. 4). This also influences the resulting accuracy of the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs as the RMSEs also depend on the number of observations per cell (Fig. 6).

Assuming approximately 80 % coverage, Pronk et al. (2024) suggested that resolutions between 200 and 700 m might be achievable with current spaceborne lidar data, depending on latitude. Our results are in line with their suggestion, showing that the optimal resolution for our study areas was 300 m, at which 80 % coverage with a density of at least 5 observations per cell and accuracy better than 5 m can be achieved (Fig. 4). While our analysis suggests that 300 m represents an optimal resolution under current GEDI and ICESat-2 data densities, this resolution remains too coarse for many practical applications compared with existing high-resolution global DEMs, such as the 30 m Copernicus DEM or the 12 m TanDEM-X DEM (Hajnsek et al., 2025). Achieving higher-resolution global DTMs with sufficient coverage will therefore require either continued collection of spaceborne lidar data or integration with existing high-resolution DEMs (see below), as exemplified by the approach used in FathomDEM (Uhe et al., 2025).

GEDI generally provided better sampling intensity than ICESat-2. This is in line with prior studies by Narin and Gullu (2023) and Pronk et al. (2024). These authors, however, did not consider the accuracy of observations. Nevertheless, we observed that the sampling coverage and density for both datasets consistently declined with more stringent accuracy thresholds. This resulted in a rapid increase in the number of observation-free cells and, in turn, in a decline in DTM accuracy (see the next section). This decline with more stringent accuracy thresholds was more pronounced for GEDI than for ICESat-2. However, combining ICESat-2 and GEDI substantially improves both coverage and density across all tested accuracy scenarios (Fig. 4). This is especially important for generating DTMs at higher spatial resolutions (as attempted in this study), for which individual datasets alone are insufficient (Narin and Gullu, 2023).

4.3. Generation of global DTMs

Our results show that interpolating a 90 m DTM using a combination

of ICESat-2 and GEDI observations is a feasible approach yielding an accuracy comparable to existing global DEMs (Figs. 6 and 7). However, the accuracy of DTMs interpolated using spaceborne lidar at such resolution is limited by the sparse sampling intensity of the ICESat-2 and GEDI observations (only 60 % of cells are covered by at least one observation). The optimal accuracy threshold for selecting spaceborne lidar observations for DTM generation was 15 m. This relatively high value was somewhat surprising; however, it is because stricter thresholds resulted in lower observation density and thus required interpolation over a larger number of cells (Figs. 6 and 7). The low sampling intensity was highlighted to be the principal limiting factor by previous studies as well (Narin and Gullu, 2023; Căţeanu and Miculescu, 2024). Indeed, DTMs accuracies improved markedly with increasing point density per cell (Fig. 6). For example, in forested areas, cells with at least 1–3 observations already performed better than the Copernicus DEM. The vertical accuracy of observations obviously also plays an important role: when using observations with vertical error lower than 5 m, RMSEs dropped below 3 m in all study areas as soon as the density reached 4–6 observations per 90 m cell, compared to RMSEs of 6–10 m when only 1–3 observations were available (Fig. 6).

Comparison with global Copernicus DEM showed that DTMs interpolated using filtered ICESat-2 and GEDI data outperformed this global DEM in forested areas. In non-forested areas, however, Copernicus DEM was more accurate than interpolated space-borne lidar DTMs (Fig. 5). A more detailed examination of individual cells showed that the quality of the DTM depends considerably on the observations density and vertical accuracy. Observations with vertical accuracies better than 5 m can provide higher accuracies than global DEMs, even in non-forested areas, provided that there are more than four observations in the cell (Fig. 6). On the other hand, given the low accuracy of global DEMs in forested areas (Gdulová et al., 2020; Marešová et al., 2024), the interpolated spaceborne lidar DTMs outperformed the Copernicus DEM even in cells with low densities (i.e., 1–3 observations per cell) and low vertical accuracy of observations in such areas (Fig. 6). This suggests that while spaceborne lidar holds promise for generating accurate DTMs, substantial improvements in sampling density will be needed to match the

resolution and accuracy of existing DEM products. Similarly, [Narin and Gullu \(2023\)](#) concluded that the performance of spaceborne lidar DTMs was lower than that of existing global DEMs at a 30 m resolution (i.e., using finer resolution than 90 m used in this study).

Alternatively, hybrid approaches, such as integration with optical or radar data, can be adopted to provide highly accurate global DEMs. Due to the aforementioned limitations in the density of highly accurate observations, this has been the prevailing approach so far. Alternatively, ICESat-2 or GEDI data can be used for estimating errors in other global DEMs and their correction ([Magruder et al., 2021](#); [Tian and Shan, 2024](#); [Guenther et al., 2024](#); [Narin et al., 2024](#); [Li et al., 2025](#); [Meadows et al., 2025](#)), or to generate truly bare-Earth models, such as, for example, FABDEM ([Hawker et al., 2022](#)), which was recently highlighted as the most accurate bare-Earth model ([Marešová et al., 2024](#)).

Whether high-resolution DTMs can be produced solely from spaceborne altimetry observations without using existing DEMs as a priori input depends on the density of available observations and, therefore, the continuation of existing missions. Both ICESat-2 and GEDI are expected to continue providing data for several more years. ICESat-2 has already surpassed its nominal mission lifetime and, based on current onboard resources and assuming no anomalies occur, it could remain operational until early to mid-2030s ([Magruder et al., 2025](#)). GEDI has completed its primary mission phase and entered hibernation, with a second mission extension initiated in 2024. If approved, a third extension could prolong operations until the 2030s. With continued data acquisition, the increasing density of observations will enhance the feasibility of generating truly bare-Earth, high-resolution DEMs in the near future. By then, we may witness a significant breakthrough in spaceborne DEM generation with the development of a constellation of satellites providing annual 3D mapping of the entire landmass of the Earth (e.g., [Lowe et al., 2024](#); [nuview.space](#)). To support the design and success of such missions, further research into the interplay between observation accuracy, sampling density, and spatial resolution will be essential.

4.4. Limitations due to difficulties in filtering ICESat-2 and GEDI observations

Our findings indicate that the accuracy of the used observations plays an important role in the quality of the interpolated DTM. Specifically, where the observations density exceeded 10 per cell, using observations with a vertical height error of less than 5 m resulted in DTMs with RMSEs of 1.9–2.8 m ([Fig. 6](#)). Remarkably, when we filtered observations using only internal quality flags, without any external reference, the resulting DTMs achieved RMSEs of 3.4–4.0 m. Although this approach did not match the performance of the S₅ scenario, it still yielded robust results, demonstrating that even without ideal filtering conditions, high-quality DTMs can be achieved. This suggests that filtering of ICESat-2 (ATL08) and GEDI (L2A) observations (i.e. application of quality flags criteria to remove unreliable observations) is crucial for obtaining accurate DTMs. This is consistent with prior research that highlighted this also for above-ground biomass estimates ([Varvia et al., 2022](#)).

Filtering out low-quality ICESat-2 and GEDI observations may serve as an effective strategy for error mitigation ([Moudrý et al., 2022, 2024](#); [Wang et al., 2022](#)). This, however, may pose a challenge in real-world practice where reference DTMs (such as ALS data used in this study) are unavailable. In practice, quality flags and auxiliary data are frequently applied to filter out low-quality ICESat-2 and GEDI observations. Moreover, these approaches are continuously evolving ([Carabajal and Boy, 2020](#); [Moudrý et al., 2022, 2024](#); [Li et al., 2024](#); [Neuenschwander et al., 2025](#)). More stringent filtering ensures the high quality of remaining observations but comes with the risk of sacrificing many good quality observations ([Varvia et al., 2022](#); [Wang et al., 2022](#)). We suggest that future research should focus on improving filtering methods for spaceborne lidar data in the absence of reference datasets

and on exploring adaptive strategies that balance data quality and sampling intensity to optimize DTM generation. For example, instead of using a global fixed accuracy threshold, thresholds could vary depending on terrain type, landcover, or observations density.

5. Conclusions

This study assessed the feasibility of generating DTMs using spaceborne lidar observations from ICESat-2 (ATL08) and GEDI (L2A) missions, with a particular focus on understanding the trade-offs between observation accuracy, sampling intensity, and spatial resolution. Our results show a clear trade-off between observation accuracy and spatial coverage: stricter accuracy thresholds reduce the number of useable observations, thereby limiting the coverage and impairing DTM accuracy due to the increased number observation-free cells. ICESat-2 data consistently provided higher accuracy in terrain height estimation than GEDI footprints across a range of conditions. However, GEDI offered higher observation density. Integrating ICESat-2 and GEDI significantly increased sampling intensity, highlighting the value of a multi-sensor approach for generating accurate DTMs.

However, reliable filtering of accurate observations in the absence of reference data (e.g. ALS DTM) remains a challenge. Both sensors showed declining accuracy with an increasing slope, although ICESat-2 was less affected. Additionally, both sensors tended to provide slightly higher accuracy in non-forested areas compared to forested ones, reflecting the challenges of detecting ground returns under dense canopy. ICESat-2 data collected during nighttime acquisitions demonstrated improved accuracy compared with daytime observations, likely due to reduced solar noise. In contrast, GEDI data showed no consistent pattern between day and night acquisitions. Beam strength also had a more pronounced impact on GEDI performance than on ICESat-2.

Under the current observation densities, optimal DTM resolution was found to be 300 m. While interpolating higher resolution DTMs at 90 m is possible, the accuracy of the resulting model varies considerably depending on the number of observations in individual cells. The DTM combining ICESat-2 and GEDI data at a resolution of 90 m outperformed Copernicus DEM in forested regions, even where observation densities were relatively low (1–3 observations per cell) and moderate accuracy thresholds (i.e., 15–20 m) were applied for observations filtering. In contrast, Copernicus DEM remained more accurate in non-forested areas unless spaceborne lidar observation density was sufficiently high (4–6 observations per cell) and filtering threshold for vertical accuracy was set to 5 m. Given the current limitations in observation density and the issues with reliable filtering of accurate measurements, the generation of DTMs at 90 m resolution using only spaceborne lidar data remains a significant challenge. Nevertheless, the continued operation and data acquisition from both the ICESat-2 and GEDI missions hold promise for progressively closing this gap in the near future.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Petra Pracná: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Eliska Šarovcová:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Data curation. **Xiao Liu:** Writing – review & editing. **Anette Eltner:** Writing – review & editing. **Jana Marešová:** Writing – review & editing. **Katerina Gdulová:** Writing – review & editing. **Mikhail Urbazaev:** Writing – review & editing. **Michele Torresani:** Writing – review & editing. **Giorgi Kozhoridze:** Writing – review & editing. **Vítězslav Moudrý:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

The spaceborne and airborne lidar data used in this study are openly available from their respective repositories.

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